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Species composition, diversity and community structure of mangroves in Barangay Fabio, Tagana-an, Surigao Del Norte, Philippines

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Abstract

Mangrove ecosystems serve a crucial environmental role in protecting coastlines from storms, floods, and erosion, and they aid as a breeding ground for many marine life. Mangrove forests are declining due to relentless anthropogenic activities. Thus, the assessment of mangrove species plays a crucial part in the upkeep and protection of the forest. This study aimed to determine species composition, diversity, and community structure of mangrove forests in Barangay. Fabio, Surigao del Norte using the line quadrat method. Results revealed that the area has very low diversity belonging to only three families, three genera, and three different species. Among the three other species, *Rhizophora apiculata* obtained the highest abundance. Results showed that the area is not diverse in terms of species composition and abundance, as shown by several indices of diversity.

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Introduction

Mangrove ecosystem plays a crucial role in maintaining environmental sustainability. Mangroves serve as a breeding ground for many marine life as well as exporters of both organic and inorganic carbon (Suman, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2017). Mangrove forests sequester large amounts of carbon from the atmosphere and into their biomass and soils, four times as much carbon per unit area compared to terrestrial forest ecosystems (Sippo *et al.*, 2018; Simard *et al.*, 2019).

With rising sea levels and unpredictable tropical storms brought upon by the changing climate, tropical and subtropical nations like the Philippines can inevitably benefit from the buffering capabilities of the root systems of mangrove trees that reduce coastal erosion rates and inland flooding (Zhang *et al.*, 2012). It can inevitably benefit from the buffering capabilities of the root systems of mangrove trees that reduce coastal erosion rates and inland flooding (Zhang *et al.*, 2012). Mangroves also provide economic support to the community. Mangrove trees are used for firewood, charcoal production, and timber for construction.

Despite these, populations of many mangrove forests are in continual decline due to anthropogenic activities, which has a detrimental effect on both ecological and economic perspectives. Mangrove sites are being converted into settlements, industrial areas, and shrimp and fish farms. All these have resulted in massive fragmentation, degradation, and pollution (Gevana *et al.*, 2019).

The Philippines has at least 39 mangrove species, but there has been about a 60% decline in mangrove forests over the past eight decades (Garcia *et al.*, 2014; Dangan-Galon *et al.*, 2016). To date, the remaining mangrove cover is estimated at 153,577 ha from the early record of 400,000 ha (FMB, 2011). The Philippines is also made up of approximately 7,600 islands which experienced frequent natural disasters such as typhoons, earthquakes, and volcanic eruptions because of their geographic locations.

Small islands also encounter other environmental issues and concerns resulting from their vulnerability to climate change and sea level rise (Szekielda, 2017). Despite the possibility that these islands are more susceptible to the detrimental effects of climate change, they are very resilient due to their high degree of hazard awareness, which may be linked to their local knowledge and experiences (Sumeldan *et al.*, 2021; Añasco *et al.*, 2021).

Surigao del Norte, composed of many small islands, was recognized as one of the areas with the most extensive mangrove cover in the Philippines (Jumawan *et al.*, 2013). One of these islands is Barangay Fabio, a relatively small community that is vulnerable to habitat degradation, impacts of climate change, and forest exploitation.

The total mangrove area in Barangay Fabio declined from 162.623 ha in 2004 to 104.15 ha in 2010. However, through combined efforts implemented by the local government and the community, there was a reported increase in mangrove cover in 2015, with an area of 185.07 ha. Nevertheless, there is still a need to develop and implement effective mangrove conservation programs. One way to achieve this is through mangrove assessment studies which can help visualize how mangrove diversity and composition have changed across space and through time and locate communities that require immediate protection (Sarker *et al.*, 2018; Sarker *et al.*, 2019).

In line with this, this study aims to determine the Diameter at Breast Height (DBH), species composition and conservation status, diversity, and community structure of mangrove forests in Barangay Fabio, Tagana-an, Surigao del Norte, Philippines.

Materials and methods

Study Area

Surigao del Norte is a province of the Philippines located in the Caraga region (Fig. 1). It comprises three major islands: Siargao, Dinagat Islands, and Bucas Grande in the Philippine Sea, and a small region at the northernmost tip of the island of Mindanao.

It is a mosaic of islands at the rim of the Asian continental shelf. One of its many islands is Barangay Fabio (9.71923° N 125.63519° E), where the study was conducted. The primary vegetation of the barangay's coastal areas is the mangroves.

A variety of marine and terrestrial ecosystems can also be seen in the area, like the lush seagrass beds, coral reefs, and caves and tunnels in its islands. The total mangrove cover in Barangay Fabio from 2004-2015 is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Geographical location of Barangay Fabio, Tagana-an, Surigao del Norte.

Physico-chemical Parameters

The different physicochemical parameters measured were dry and wet temperature, pH, and humidity.

Mangrove Survey

A 100 m baseline was first established parallel to the shoreline. Three transect lines were set perpendicular to the baseline at a 50 m distance apart. In each transect, five 10 m x 10 m quadrats were laid-out at 20-meter distance end to end seaward.

The three quadrats established parallel to the baseline were constructed 10 meters from it (Fig. 3). Trees greater than or equal to 4 cm were identified and recorded, and the breast height diameter (DBH) was measured in each quadrat. Mangrove seedlings within each quadrat area were counted separately and recorded.

Plant Identification

Individual plants found within the plot were identified following the nomenclature of Tomlinson (1986), Feller and Sitnik (1996), Primavera *et al.* (2004), and Primavera and Sadaba (2012). For each transect line, basic vegetation parameters such as the diameter at breast height (dbh), and basal area were measured.

Data and Analysis

The diversity indices such as species richness, relative abundance, Shannon-Weiner diversity index, and evenness were calculated using the Paleontological Statistical Software Package (PAST) developed by Hammer *et al.* (2001).

Basal Area (m²)

The Diameter at Breast Height (DBH) was used to calculate the Basal Area with the formula:

$$\text{Basal Area} = \pi * [(\text{Average DBH} \div 2) \div 100]^2$$

Fig. 2. The total mangrove cover in Barangay Fabio from 2004-2015.

Fig. 3. The three transect lines and the five quadrats with their corresponding measurement and position

Results and discussion

Three (3) mangrove species are identified in Barangay Fabio, Surigao del Norte mangrove forest, namely *Rhizophora apiculata*, *Aegiceras corniculatum* and *Rhizophora mucronata*. These species are from two (2) families: Rhizophoraceae and Primulaceae (Table 1). All three species of mangroves are categorized as Least Concern (LC) which means that these species are still not the focus of species conservation efforts.

The number of mangrove species found in Barangay Fabio is lower than other mangrove areas in the Philippines because this is a reforested area. A study conducted in Barangay Imelda, Dinagat Island, identified a total of 10 mangrove species, while another study conducted in an estuarine area of Maligaya, Palanan, Isabela revealed 14 species of mangroves (Canizares & Seronay, 2016; Baleta & Casalमितao, 2016; Cudiamat & Rodriguez, 2017; Castillo *et al.*, 2018; Lillo *et al.*, 2019).

Table 1. Species composition and conservation status of mangroves in Barangay Fabio, Taganaan, Surigao del Norte.

N	Family	Mangrove species	Local name	Conservation status (IUCN*)
1	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i>	Bakhaw lalaki	Least concern
2	Primulaceae	<i>Aegiceras corniculatum</i>	Saging-saging	Least concern
3	Rhizophoraceae	<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	Bakhaw babae	Least concern

* www.iucnredlist.org

A total of 432 mangrove individuals were recorded in Barangay Fabio. Table 2 shows the total number of

individuals of each of the three mangrove species found in Brgy. Fabio. Bakhaw-lalaki (*Rhizophora apiculata*) has the highest number of individuals compared to the other two species. Among the three transect lines, the highest total count of Bakhaw-lalaki is found in Transect 3, with a total of 163 individuals, followed by Transect 2, with 160 individuals and the lowest count was recorded in Transect 1, with 103 individuals.

Rhizophora mucronata mangrove species were only observed in Transect 2 with only two individuals while the remaining transects have zero counts of this mangrove species. Saging-saging (*Aegiceras corniculatum*) was only present in Transect 1 with only four individuals, while the rest of the remaining transects have no record of *Aegiceras corniculatum*.

The high number of *R. apiculata* is consistent with other studies conducted in Barangay Imelda, Dinagat Island, and Honda Bay, Philippines, which also showed this specific type of mangrove as the most abundant species (Canizares & Seronay, 2016; Castillo *et al.*, 2018). *R. apiculata*, locally known as Bakhaw lalaki, can withstand high currents and tides (Robertson and Alongi, 1992).

Table 2. Population of the three mangrove species: *Rhizophora mucronata*, *Aegiceras corniculatum* and *Rhizophora apiculata*.

Species	No. of Individual			Total
	Transect 1	Transect 2	Transect 3	
<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i>	103	160	163	426
<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	0	2	0	2
<i>Aegiceras corniculatum</i>	4	0	0	4
Total				432

Fig. 4 shows that *R. apiculata* species is the most abundant mangrove species in Zones 1-5. Zone 4 has the most *R. apiculata*, with a total of 112 individuals, followed by Zone 3, which covers 88 individuals. It is then followed by Zone 5 and Zone 2 with 81 and 78 individuals, respectively. Zone 1 contains the least number of trees, with 67 individuals of *R. apiculata* species.

Fig. 4. Zonation of mangrove species from landward to seaward portions of the study site.

Table 3 shows the number of saplings that were found on the site. The saplings were only observed in Transect 3, while no saplings can be seen in Transects 1 and 2. The highest count of saplings in Transect 3 is in Quadrat 2, with 21 saplings, and the lowest number of saplings was in Quadrat 4 (3 saplings).

Many mangrove ecologists and planting practitioners have recommended moderate salinity conditions in obtaining mangrove saplings with optimum growth and high vigor in plant areas. Based on some studies, mangrove saplings' optimum growth changes their favorable salinity from low to moderate after 4 to 5 months of age (Kodikara *et al.*, 2017). According to other studies, as salinities increase, most of the settled mangrove saplings will die, and as the soil salinity decreases, new mangrove saplings grow. The more saline, the higher is the pH (Cardona & Botero, 1998). The saplings of mangrove species are affected by the site's chemical and physical attributes. Table 3 shows that the presence of saplings can only be found in transect three, which occurs in abundance compared to other transects with no saplings. However, the identification of the species of the saplings was not included in the study. Diameter at Breast Height is highest in Transect 1 at 9.86 followed by Transect 2 at 8.79cm and Transect 3 at 8.13cm (Table 4). The Basal Area was highest at Transect 1 with 0.007636m² followed by Transect 2 and Transect 3 with

the recorded area of 0.006068m² and 0.005191m², respectively. The basal area, DBH, and the number of saplings can be used to assess how mature a mangrove area is (Snedaker and Snedaker, 1984). Transect 3 has the lowest basal area, which is also where the saplings are found, suggesting that Transect 3 contains young mangroves. The calculated mean basal area of the mangrove forest in Barangay Fabio was smaller than that of the mangrove forest in Calatagan, Batangas, Verde Island Passage which has a recorded basal area of 0.0164 m² (Cudiamat and Rodriguez, 2017).

Table 3. Number of Mangrove saplings in Brgy. Fabio from Transect 1 to Transect 3.

Cuadrat	No. of saplings		
	Transect 1	Transect 2	Transect 3
1	0	0	18
2	0	0	21
3	0	0	15
4	0	0	3
5	0	0	5

Table 4. Diameter at Breast Height and Basal Area of Mangroves.

Transect No.	Mean DBH (cm)	Mean Basal Area (m ²)
1	9.86	0.007636
2	8.79	0.006068
3	8.13	0.005191
Grand Mean	8.93	0.006263

Among the three species that can be found in the study area from transect 1 to transect 3, *Rhizophora apiculata* mangrove species has the dominant number with a total of 426 species, while *Aegiceras corniculatum* mangrove species, only four were found in cuadrat 1 of transect 1, followed by *Rhizophora mucronata* mangrove species which has the lowest number.

Fig. 5. Percent composition of mangrove families in Barangay Fabio, Surigao del Norte, Philippines.

Percent Relative Abundance

Fig. 5 shows the relative abundance of each mangrove species recorded in the sampling area. Among the three species of mangroves, *R. apiculata* obtained the highest percent relative abundance (98.61%). On the other hand, the two species received the lowest value, that is, *A. corniculatum* (0.926%) and *R. mucronata* (0.463%).

Most typical types of mangroves have gone through the progression of adaptation and evolution, being capable of enduring and precipitating sludge along with a screening of contaminated materials (Purnobasuki *et al.*, 2018). *Rhizophora apiculata* is one of the most prevalent plant species in the mangrove areas of Surigao del Norte had the highest relative abundance. Its wood has high intrinsic energy value, making it an attractive energy source as firewood and for producing charcoal.

River mangrove or *Aegiceras corniculatum* grows well on drained mud intermittently swamped by saline or brackish water. Their roots are exposed to air at low tide and aid oxygen uptake. This species offers spawning grounds for juvenile commercial and recreational fish and is appropriate for restoring and maintaining river banks and estuaries. *Rhizophora mucronata* has the lowest relative abundance; this red mangrove wood is identified as very firm, dense with no water permeability, and impervious to borer invasion.

Fig. 6. Diversity indices in 3 transect lines of mangrove area in Barangay Fabio, Surigao del Norte, Philippines.

The sampling site has a species richness of 3 which means three species of mangroves are present in the area.

Species richness measures the number of species found in a sample, indicating that the more species present in a sample, the richer the sample. In addition, evenness is a measure of the relative abundance of the different species making up the richness of an area. Transect one recorded a species richness of 2, evenness 0.1453, and Shannon index of 0.15966, while transect two recorded a species richness of 2, evenness 0.7555, and Shannon index of 0.83024. On the other hand, transect three recorded the least species richness of 1, evenness 0.7246, and Shannon index of 0.7964 (Fig. 6).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the mangrove forest of Brgy. Fabio, Surigao del Norte falls under very low diversity belonging to only three families. Among the three different species, *Rhizophora apiculata* is the most dominant plant species with the utmost percent relative abundance of 98.61. Of the three stations, transect 3 has the most number of saplings with a mean pH of 5.46, which favors the growth of many saplings. The three species vary in abundance in relation to the three other stations. Results showed that the area is not diverse in terms of species composition and abundance, as shown by numerous diversity indices. As a recommendation, mangrove planting activities that will be conducted in the study area should emphasize increasing the diversity of the mangrove forest, which can be done through additional research on mangrove ecology.

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